

Feedback Form: GABI Guide

FREE AND INFORMED CONSENT FORM (FICF)

Survey Title: Expert Assessment of the GABI Guide (Welcoming Guide to Banking for Seniors)

1. Invitation and Introduction

Dear Expert,

You are invited to participate, as a volunteer, in the validation research for the "GABI Guide – Welcoming Guide to Banking for Seniors." This project corresponds to my Final Coursework (TCC) in Software Engineering. Your participation is invaluable to the quality and relevance of this study.

2. Research Objectives

The main objective of this research is to collect qualified feedback from experts in areas such as UX/UI Design, Usability, Accessibility, and Development to evaluate and improve the GABI Guide guidelines and platform. The guide aims to be a practical tool to assist in the creation of more welcoming and intuitive mobile internet banking interfaces for those aged 60 and over.

3. Participation Procedures

Your participation will consist of two main stages:

Review of the Guide: You will receive a link to freely navigate the GABI Guide website, exploring its content, the presented guidelines, and the interactive components.

Completing the Form: After reviewing the guide, you will be invited to complete an online form with your impressions, criticisms, and suggestions about the platform and its content.

The estimated total time for your participation is approximately 15 to 20 minutes.

4. Risks and Discomfort

There are no significant risks associated with this research. The only anticipated discomfort is the time spent analyzing and completing the form. You may discontinue your participation at any time if you experience any discomfort.

5. Benefits

Although there are no direct financial benefits to you as a participant, your contribution will help validate and improve an academic resource with the potential to positively impact the development of more inclusive and accessible technologies. The results may benefit designers, developers, and especially the elderly population by promoting better design practices.

6. Confidentiality and Privacy

Any and all information collected in this research is strictly confidential. Your name and other personally identifiable information will not be disclosed at any stage of the research or in its final publication. The data will be analyzed in an aggregated and anonymous form and will be used solely for the academic purposes of this Final Project.

7. Voluntary Participation

Your participation is completely voluntary. You have the right to refuse to participate, withdraw your consent, and discontinue your participation at any time, without incurring any penalty or detriment.

8. Contact Information

If you have any questions about the research, you can contact the lead researcher at: xxxxxxxx.

Link to the guide: GABI

* **Indica uma pergunta obrigatória**

1. Do you agree to the terms? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

Link to the website

CATEGORIAS

Tamanho e Layout

Elementos Visuais

Navegação e
Interação

Feedback e Erros

Segurança e
ConfiançaAprendizagem e
SuporteFuncionalidades e
ConteúdoRecomendações
Gerais**GABI: Guia Acolhedor de Banking para Idosos**

O GABI (Guia de Acolhedor de Banking para Idosos) é um projeto de Trabalho de Conclusão de Curso (TCC) desenvolvido com base em uma revisão sistemática da literatura (RSL) e em uma pesquisa direta com usuários idosos. Esse guia prático reúne diretrizes fundamentadas em evidências científicas e na experiência real da população 60+, visando apoiar o desenvolvimento de interfaces digitais de Internet Banking que sejam acessíveis, intuitivas e acolhedoras para esse público. O GABI oferece recomendações claras para que desenvolvedores, designers e instituições financeiras possam criar plataformas digitais inclusivas, facilitando o acesso dos idosos aos serviços bancários online com segurança, autonomia e confiança.

Categorias de Diretrizes

Tamanho e Layout

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Aprendizagem e Suporte

Funcionalidades e Conteúdo

Recomendações Gerais

LINK TO THE GUIDE

[GABI - Guia Acolhedor de Banking para Idosos](#)

2. Start feedback? *

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Yes *Pular para a pergunta 3*

No *Pular para a pergunta 2*

Section 1: Expert Profile

3. Main Area of Expertise:

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- UX Design
- UI Design
- User Researcher
- Aecessibility
- Front-end development
- Back-end development
- Outro: _____

4. Years of Experience in the Field: *

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- 1-3 years
- 4-7 years
- 8-12 years
- More than 12 years

Overall Platform Assessment (UX/UI and Presentation)

Please rate the following aspects of the platform on a scale of 1 (Very Poor) to 5 (Excellent).

5. Clarity of Navigation and Information Architecture *

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1 2 3 4 5

Very Excellent

6. Visual Design and Aesthetics (UI) *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Excellent

7. Usability and Ease of Interaction (including interactive components) *

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1 2 3 4 5

Very Excellent

8. Responsiveness and Mobile Experience *

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1 2 3 4 5

Very Excellent

9. Any comments or improvements regarding the aspects mentioned?

Content Assessment (Guidelines Quality)

Now, focusing on the content of the guide, evaluate the following criteria

10. **Clarity and Understanding of the Guidelines Presented:** *

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- Very Hard to Understand
- A Little Confused
- Clear and Direct
- Very Clear and Didactic
- Outro: _____

11. **Relevance and Usefulness of the Guidelines for Product Development for the 60+ Audience:** *

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1 2 3 4 5

Not Very relevant

12. **Which guideline or section did you find most impactful or well-presented? Why?**

13. **Are there any guidelines you think could be improved, or any important information that is missing?**

Open Feedback and Suggestions

This section is for your final thoughts.

14. What was your overall impression of the GABI project?

15. Did you encounter any bugs, typos, or technical issues while browsing? If so, please describe them.

16.

Do you have any final suggestions for improving the guide, whether in terms of design, content, or functionality?

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